

University of Mumbai

University of Mumbai

Inter-Collegiate / Institute / Department Research Convention
(Zonal Round)
Academic Year : 2023-24

Certificate of Participation

This is to Certify that **Dr. Amanulla Khan** of **Anjuman Islam Janjira Degree College of Science, Janjira** has guided a Research Project titled **Aquaponics for Sustainable Food Production** which was presented by his student **Ms. Fahim aisha Shakeel** in **Agriculture and Animal Husbandry** Category and **UG** Level at 18th Aavishkar: Inter-Collegiate / Institute / Department Research Convention (Zonal Round) organized by the University of Mumbai at M.B. More Foundation's Arts, Commerce and Science Women College, Roha (Dhatav), Dist.-Raigad on December 4, 2023 for **Raigad** zone.

Dr. Minakshi Gurav
OSD,
Aavishkar,
University of Mumbai

Dr. Sunil Patil
Director,
Department of Students' Development,
University of Mumbai

December 4, 2023
Roha (Dhatav), Dist.-Raigad

